

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins. Part XI*: Synthesis of Benzofuro (3,2-c) benzopyrones

V. N. Dholakia and K. N. Trivedi

Different 4-hydroxycoumarins are dehydrogenatively coupled with catechol to give corresponding benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran derivatives (I).

Coumaronocoumarins is a group of naturally occurring substances such as coumestrol (Ia), wedelolactone, psoralidin etc. They are also of structural interest because they are related to substances of coumaronochroman and 3-arylcoumarin types. Coumaronocoumarins are generally synthesised by the action of aniline hydrochlorides or pyridine hydrochloride on suitably substituted 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarins. Wanzlick *et al.*¹ synthesised welelactone by the dehydrogenative coupling of catechol with 4,5-dihydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin in the presence of potassium ferricyanide or potassium iodate.

In the present work, we report here the dehydrogenative coupling of catechol with substituted 4-hydroxycoumarins to give coumaronocoumarins of type (I).

- I. a. $R = R_3 = \text{OH}$; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = \text{H}$
 b. $R = R_1 = \text{OH}$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$; $R_4 = \text{CH}_3$
 c. $R_1 = \text{OCH}_3$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$; $R_4 = \text{CH}_3$
 d. $R = R_1 = \text{OCH}_3$; $R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = \text{H}$; $R_4 = \text{OCH}_3$
 e. $R = R_1 = \text{OCH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$; $R_4 = R_5 = \text{H}$
 f. $R = R_1 = \text{OCH}_3$; $R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$; $R_5 = \text{OCH}_3$
 g. $R = R_1 = \text{OCH}_3$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$; $R_4 = R_5 = \text{H}$

4-Hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin² on condensation with catechol in the presence of potassium iodate and sodium acetate gave 2-methyl-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro (3,2-c) benzopyran (Ib) which on methylation with dimethyl sulphate in acetone gave 2-methyl-8,9-dimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzopyro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Ic).

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2. V. R. Shah, J. L. Bose and R. C. Shah, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 677.

4-Hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin³, 4-hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin⁴, 4-hydroxy-5-methoxycoumarin⁵ and 4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin were similarly condensed with catechol and subsequently methylated to give 2,8,9-trimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Id), 4-methyl-3,8,9-trimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Ie), 1,8,9-trimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (If) and 3,4,8,9-tetramethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Ig) respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Ib): To the solution of 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (0.8 g.), catechol (0.4 g.) and sodium acetate (2.0 g.) in acetone-water (20 ml.; 1 : 1), a solution of potassium iodate (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (1.0 g.) in water (10 ml.) was added slowly with constant stirring. After 5 mins the separated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 348°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 68.00; H, 3.11. $C_{16}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 68.00; H, 3.57%).

2-Methyl-8,9-dimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Ic): A mixture of 2-methyl-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (0.4 g.), dimethyl sulfate (1 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 8 hrs. On evaporation of acetone, the separated product was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 210°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 69.31; H, 4.56. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 69.67; H, 4.55%).

2-Methoxy-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran: To the solution of 4-hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin (1.0 g.), catechol (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (2.5 g.) in acetone water (25 ml.; 1 : 1) a solution of potassium iodate (0.6 g.) and sodium acetate (1.2 g.) in water (10 ml.) was added slowly with constant stirring. The product which separated immediately was worked up as before, m.p. > 320°. It could not be crystallised from any solvent.

2,8,9-Trimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Id): A mixture of 2-methoxy-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (0.4 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for about 10 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and the product crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 240°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 66.24; H, 4.29. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 66.25; H, 4.32%).

4-Methyl-8,9-dihydroxy-3-methoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran: To the solution of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin (0.5 g.), catechol (0.2 g.) and sodium acetate (1.2 g.) in water acetone (10 ml.; 1 : 1) a solution of potassium iodate (0.3 g.) and sodium acetate (0.6 g.) in water (5 ml.) was added slowly with constant stirring and the reaction mixture worked up as before, m.p. > 320°. It could not be crystallised from any solvent.

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4. V. N. Gupta, B. R. Sharma and R. B. Aurora, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 406.
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4-Methyl-3,8,9-trimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Ie): A mixture of 4-methyl-8,9-dihydroxy-3-methoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c) benzopyran (0.5 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1.0 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) in dry acetone (150 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 10 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and the product crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 232°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 66.79; H, 4.68. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 67.05; H, 4.75%).

1-Methoxy-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran: To the solution of 4-hydroxy-5-methoxycoumarin (0.6 g.), catechol (0.3 g.) and sodium acetate (1.5 g.) in acetone water (10 ml., 1 : 1), a solution of potassium iodate (0.35 g.) and sodium acetate (0.75 g.) in water (6 ml.) was added slowly with constant stirring and worked out as before, m.p. > 320°.

1,8,9-Trimethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (If): A mixture of 1-methoxy-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c) benzopyran (0.3 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and the product crystallised from benzene, m.p. 263°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 65.97; H, 4.11. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 66.25; H, 4.32%).

3,4-Dimethoxy-8,9-dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran: To a solution of 4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (0.8 g.), catechol (0.4 g.) and sodium acetate (2.0 g.) in acetone water (20 ml.; 1 : 1), a solution of potassium iodate (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (1.0 g.) in water (10 ml.) was added slowly with constant stirring. The reaction was worked up as before, m.p. > 300°.

3,4,8,9-Tetramethoxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (Ig): A mixture of 3,4-dimethoxy and dihydroxy-6-oxo-6H-benzofuro(3,2-c)benzopyran (0.5 g.) dimethyl sulphate (1 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 8 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and the product crystallised from benzene petroleum ether, m.p. 204°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 63.93; H, 4.73. $C_{19}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 64.04; H, 4.53%).

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